

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

SOME LEGAL AND COMMERCIAL ASPECTS OF THE ELECTRONIC BILL OF LADING

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Abstract

The transition from traditional paper bills of lading to electronic formats is changing international maritime transport. This article examines the role of electronic Bills of Lading in documentation procedures and enhancing operational efficiency across global supply chains. By eliminating the inefficiencies and risks associated with physical courier services and manual documentation, eB/Ls offer instant, secure, and cost-effective transfer of ownership and shipment details. The adoption of standardized eB/Ls, facilitated by initiatives such as the DCSA Digital Trade program, promises to revolutionize trade documentation processes, promote transparency, reliability, and sustainability. Furthermore, the introduction of electronic freight options, supported by robust theoretical frameworks, presents new avenues for managing freight risk and optimizing trading strategies in the dynamic shipping market. This article examines the role of electronic trade documentation and discusses the need for international cooperation to overcome legal and technical obstacles to their adoption.

Keywords: Electronic Bills of Lading (eB/Ls); DCSA Digital Trade program, International trade logistics; Digital transformation; Freight risk management, UNICITRAL Model Law on Electronic Transferable Records (MLETR); Global adoption, Trade documentation revolution; FFAs; Asian-Style Options

1. Simplifying International Trade: The Role of Standard Electronic Bills of Lading

In container shipping, the Bill of Lading is the most important transport and trade document. In order to submit the original papers to the importer during the transport process, traders who are involved in supply chains and use original B/L have to arrange courier delivery for the documents, which is expensive and opens the door to fraud. You may use a paperless Seaway Bill or an electronic Telex release for Bill of Lading, but the lack of standard data formats and procedures creates uncertainty, leading to shipping inconsistencies, operational delays, revenue losses, and increased expenses.

The goal of the Digital Trade program of the Digital Container Shipping Association (DCSA) was to make things easier for a standards-based electronic Bill of Lading to be adopted globally, which would apply to both Seaway Bills and original Bills of Ladings. The DCSA B/L standard removes paper and manual involvement from B/L procedures by enabling straight-through processing of B/L data through open-source Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). Standardized digitalization of B/L data and procedures will help develop an environment for a more safe, flexible, and sustainable supply chain. In order to enable the smooth

digital transfer of original B/L across various platforms and stakeholders, DCSA is also closely collaborating with eBL solution providers on technical and legal interoperability. This will help to accelerate the adoption of B/L standards throughout the world.[1]

2. Five Major particulars concerning Electronic Bills of Lading

The days of exchanging actual paper money and sending it via a physical courier may be coming to an end as more and more digital courier firms enter the market. The COVID pandemic has sped up the use of electronic bills of lading, leading to a far greater acceptance of this option within the shipping sector. Before joining the world of electronic bills of lading services, whether you are a bank, an importer, an exporter, a freight forwarder, or a service provider for international trade between importers and exporters, make sure they are familiar with the subject. [2]

- A contemporary, digital method of B/L transfer is provided by eB/L services.

Instant, Authentic Transfer: eB/L services offer a contemporary, digital alternative to traditional paper bills, ensuring instant and authentic transfer via blockchain or cloud-based technology.

- In terms of speed, cost, and security, eB/L is better than shifted by paper/courier.

Enhanced Speed, Cost Savings, and Security: eB/L eliminates the drawbacks of physical courier services, providing faster transfer times, significant cost savings, and heightened security against loss, forgery, or damage.

- eB/Ls - safeguard company continuity

Continuity Assurance: With eB/L securely stored in the cloud or on blockchain networks, businesses are safeguarded against disruptions caused by misplaced or damaged paper bills, ensuring seamless trade operations.

- eB/L - provide increased security and comfort

Robust Security Measures: Digitally signed, encrypted, and securely stored, eB/L virtually eliminates the risk of falsification or theft, offering unparalleled security and privacy, particularly in blockchain-based systems.

- eB/L - can solve the short route issue

Efficient Resolution of Short Route Issues: eB/L facilitate the smooth release of shipments, even on short legs, by bypassing the delays associated with paper-based documentation, ensuring timely delivery and cost-effective operations.

3. How the Shipping Process is improved by the Electronic Bill of Lading

Innovative Electronic Bill of Lading Technology to Simplify International Trade Recent technological developments have resulted in the electronic Bill of Lading (eB/L) format replacing the conventional paper Bill of Lading. Other names for this innovative technology include E Bill of Lading, Electronic Bill, and Digital Bill of Lading. By increasing efficiency and transparency, the new Electronic Bills of Lading simplify documentation procedures and operations for all parties involved in the supply chain, such as banks, insurance providers, and freight forwarders. [3]

A Bill of Lading: What Is It? -The document that the carrier of goods issues to the "shipper" of the cargo is called a bill of lading. This paper serves as proof of shipment or evidence. An electronic bill of lading, or eB/L, is what? - A newly created electronic Bill of Lading is known as an electronic Bill of Lading. The eB/L enhances information speed, security, and accuracy while fulfilling the same tasks for the logistics industry.

Transitioning to an Electronic Bill of Lading procedure offers significant advantages to every link in the supply chain. Logistics operations become more efficient than before as a result of the time saved on manual documentation, the decreased chance of errors, and the improved data security.

If 50% of all Bills of Lading were processed electronically. The worldwide container shipping sector could save up to \$4 billion annually, according to the Digital Container Shipping Association. This is a significant figure because, in the case of international supply chain shipments, the Bill of Lading influences numerous parties' unique procedures and workflows. Shippers will give carriers the necessary information and data to construct the Bill of Lading, which can then be shared with banks, consignees, freight forwarders, and many other supply chain participants with ease.

Electronic Bills of Lading (eB/L) revolutionize supply chain workflows by eliminating paper-based processes. With eB/Ls, data entry, electronic stamps, and digital signatures streamline ownership transfer, reducing administrative time and costs. Integration with software systems such as TMSs, ERPs, and CRMs facilitates instant data sharing, eliminating human errors and the need for physical document exchange. This paperless procedure enhances efficiency, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness throughout the supply chain, marking a significant leap towards digital transformation in international trade.

The transition to Electronic Bills of Lading (eB/L) faces legal complexities requiring international collaboration. Each nation must enact legislation to recognize eBLs, posing challenges due to varying legal systems. The UNICITRAL's Model Law on Electronic Transferable Records (MLETR) serves as a blueprint for legal reforms, facilitating eB/L adoption. Notable adopters of the MLETR include Bahrain, Belize, Estonia, Finland, France, Kribati, Papua New Guinea, United Arab Emirates, Paraguay, Denmark, Singapore, and the United Kingdom, signaling a global shift towards embracing digital trade documentation.

3. BIMCO's eB/L Standard

The eBL Standard is a structured dataset consisting of 20 predefined data fields common to bulk shipping bills of lading, for example, CONGENBILL. The underlying framework applies equally to BIMCO's various bills of lading and other bulk bills of lading. The standard is freely available to eBL solution providers to download from [BIMCO's website](#).

BIMCO introduces the electronic bill of lading standard (eB/L Standard) to accelerate digitalization in bulk shipping. Featuring 20 preset data fields tailored for bulk shipping bills, the structured dataset aims to establish common industry standards. Despite existing reliable platforms, less than 2% of global seaborne trade employs eB/Ls, hindered by interoperability challenges. BIMCO's initiative addresses this by creating a technological standard, ensuring seamless transfer between systems. As a founding member of the FIT Alliance, BIMCO collaborates with industry leaders to align standards such as the UN/CEFACT Multimodal Transport Reference Data Model and DCSA. The architecture of the eBL Standard aligns with existing bills of lading, facilitating widespread adoption across. [4]

(Ali Abbas Khayoon, 2020), The Baltic and International Maritime Council (BIMCO) Electronic Bills of Lading Clause 2014 is a contractual clause designed to address the increasing use of electronic documentation, particularly in the dry cargo sector. It was published in BIMCO Special Circular No. 3, 20 May 2014, and is an express clause that needs to be incorporated into charter parties if the parties intend that charterers will have the right to order owners to issue electronic Bills of Lading (eB/L).

The clause states that at the Charterers' option, bills of lading, waybills, and delivery orders should be issued, signed, and transmitted in electronic form with the same effect as their paper equivalent. Owners are required to subscribe to and use Electronic (Paperless)

Trading Systems as directed by the Charterers, provided such systems are approved by the International Group of P&I Clubs. Any fees incurred in subscribing to or using such systems will be for the Charterers' account.

BIMCO emphasizes that charterers, their sub-charterers, and others in a charter party chain must fully understand the need to sign up for the chosen system or systems if they want to benefit from paperless trading procedures. The International Group of P&I Clubs has approved five paperless trading systems, Bolero, essDOCS, E-Title, edoxOnline, and Wave.

The BIMCO Electronic Bills of Lading Clause is merely a contractual clause, not a service provider of electronic bills of lading like KTNET, Bolero, essDOCS, E-Title, edoxOnline, and Wave. [5]

To date, the International Group of P&I Clubs has approved their Members' use of the eBL systems of the following providers; Bolero, CargoX, edoxOnline, essDOCS, e-Title, IQAX, TradeLens and WAVE. Additional information on eBLs is available below on the Club's website. [6]

5. EU regulations on electronic freight transport information

Regulation (EU) 2020/1056 on electronic freight transport information a legal framework that allows economic operators to share with enforcement authorities information in an electronic format concerning the transport of goods by road, rail, inland waterways and air in the European Union (EU).

Application:

The regulation applies to regulatory information requirements on the transport of goods set out in the EU legal acts listed in points 1-5 below and to regulatory information requirements laid down in delegated or implementing acts adopted by the European Commission in accordance with the legal acts listed under points 1-7 below (listed in Part A of Annex I):

1. EEC Council Regulation No 11 on inland navigation ;
2. Council Directive 92/106/EEC on intermodal transport;
3. Regulation (EC) No 1072/2009 on international road haulage;
4. Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 on waste shipments;
5. Directive 2008/68/EC on inland transport of dangerous goods;
6. Directive (EU) 2016/797 on the interoperability of the rail system;
7. Regulation (EC) No 300/2008 on civil aviation security.

The regulation also applies to similar information requirements in relevant national laws (listed in Part B of Annex I).

Electronic freight transport information (eFTI)

Electronic freight transport information (eFTI) is a set of data elements processed electronically to exchange regulatory information among economic operators (mainly companies involved in freight transport and logistics) and between operators and competent authorities.[7]

6. Advantages and disadvantages of electronic Bill of Lading

(Wunderlich, S., & Saive, D., 2020), The use of electronic B/L allows for rapid creation, transfer, and verification of correctness, as it eliminates the need for paper-based processes and the interruptions they cause. The complete transfer of the document is therefore significantly expedited and more robust. This issue of delivery without the submission of the Bill of Lading can also be resolved using this method. Utilizing a blockchain-based method addresses the aforementioned issue by facilitating the generation and exchange of digital tokens that accurately represent tangible assets. These tokens will serve as electronic bills of lading. Nevertheless, the platform will be designed to be application-neutral in order to establish a universal standard for all types of token-based trading. The continuous legal oversight of the development work guarantees that the software consistently adheres to legal regulations.

The utilization of paper-based transport documentation, which is both costly and time-consuming, is in direct opposition to the effective and efficient functioning of the transport sector. If the documentation of transport processes can be fully digitized, cargo means such as containers can be reintroduced into circulation at an earlier stage. Additionally, this digital process significantly reduces the duration that ships remain in port, as the verification and approval of documents can be completed entirely through digital means, taking only a few seconds. Ultimately, the working conditions aboard the ship are enhanced, allowing the crew to fully focus on ensuring the safety and efficiency of the traffic.

The limitations of the BOLERO approach are based on the requirement that electronic B/L can only achieve widespread success if there is guaranteed international and independent access that is both affordable and easily accessible. Hence, the implementation of electronic B/L requires consideration not only of technical aspects, but also of operational and managerial factors. The responsibility for managing the electronic bill of lading should be given to an internationally operating, non-profit organization. This independent organization encompasses private sector entities involved in the international sea freight industry, along with international organizations such as IMO, and national and supranational authorities. Their collective goal is to ensure widespread acceptance of the market within the maritime sector. [8]

BIMCO, Electronic issuance of bills of lading has been feasible for over two decades. Although there are secure and widely recognized platforms that have been authorized by the International Group of P&I Clubs, less than 2% of global maritime trade is conducted using electronic bills of lading (eB/L). A recognized barrier to broader adoption of eB/L is the current inability to transfer an eBL from one authorized platform to another, known as a lack of interoperability. Trade finance banks face a specific challenge when shifting from paper bills to electronic bills of lading (eBLs), as it necessitates training their staff to use various platforms, even though the number of eB/L being processed is very small. To transfer an electronic bill of

lading (eB/L) between platforms, it is necessary for the eB/L to be in the same digital format, which is achieved by adopting a specific technical standard. The initial stage involves the creation and implementation of a standardized framework. [9]

(Goldby, M., 2011), Documents of title, including the bill of lading, have served crucial practical purposes in the business world for many centuries. In the past, bills of lading, along with other documents of title, obtained their ability to transfer rights contained within them through commercial customs. Numerous legal rulings in the common law system pertain to bills of exchange and bills of lading, which are widely utilized documents in international trade. These rulings often make reference to the historical background of these documents. The use of bills of lading in commerce was transnational, meaning it was a part of mercantile law that applied across different countries. The bill of lading was recognized as having the ability to achieve similar effects when transferred in various jurisdictions worldwide. This was crucial for facilitating smooth cross-border trade. The bill of lading arose in response to commercial demands and became a recognized instrument that various countries' laws eventually acknowledged as having the ability to achieve specific effects attributed to it by merchants' customs. [10]

Conclusion:

- Standardized electronic Bills of Lading (eB/Ls) streamline international trade logistics, offering instant, secure, and transparent data transfer, thereby enhancing supply chain efficiency and sustainability.
- Initiatives like the DCSA Digital Trade program drive standardization efforts for eB/Ls, promoting interoperability and facilitating seamless data exchange among stakeholders, thereby improving efficiency and transparency in global trade
- Initiatives like the DCSA Digital Trade program drive standardization efforts for eB/Ls, promoting interoperability and facilitating seamless data exchange among stakeholders, thereby improving efficiency and transparency in global trade.
- Despite the transformative potential of electronic trade documentation, challenges such as legal complexities and interoperability issues persist. International collaboration and regulatory harmonization are crucial to overcoming these challenges and ensuring the seamless integration of electronic trade documentation into global trade practices.
- The ongoing digital transformation of trade documentation holds immense potential to revolutionize

international trade logistics, fostering efficiency, transparency, and sustainability across supply chains. Continued efforts towards standardization, collaboration, and innovation are imperative to fully realize the benefits of electronic trade documentation in the years to come.

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